

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE AND ALKYL IODIDES. PART III. CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF A WEAK ACID.

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A detailed study of the hydrogen ion catalysis in the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction is made by using a weak acid (acetic) as a source of the catalyst. The hydrogen ion concentration is controlled by the addition of neutral salts, sodium acetate and by varying the concentration of the acid itself. "Secondary electrolyte effect" is observed in presence of neutral salts. The catalytic coefficients of acetate ions and of molecules of undissociated acetic acid have also been determined. The reaction is accelerated by hydrogen and acetate ions and retarded by molecules of undissociated acetic acid.

In continuation of our previous communication (Telang and Nadkarny, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 536) a more extensive study of the hydrogen ion catalysis has been made by employing a weak acid like acetic acid as a source of the catalyst. Incidentally, the study of the catalysis by all ions and molecules is made.

With acetic acid as the source of the catalyst

$$K' = \frac{C_{R^+} C_{A^-}}{C_{HA}} \cdot f_{R^+} f_{A^-}$$

(*vide* Moelwyn-Hughes, "Kinetics of Reactions in Solution", 1933), both activity coefficients decrease with the addition of neutral salts, so that an increase in C_{R^+} is anticipated and the "secondary salt effect" should be positive. Brönsted and La Mer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 555) have applied these considerations to the catalytic decomposition of diazoacetic ester by hydrogen ion. Dawson and Lowson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 393, 1217) found in the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate by means of three different acids (acetic, glycollic and dichloroacetic) in the presence of sodium chloride that the reaction velocity at first increased with increasing concentration of salt. The concentration of hydrogen ion has been obtained by means of the relation $k'' = k[H^+]$, where k'' is the catalytic coefficient of Bredig and Fraenkel (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1905, **11**, 525) independent of the nature of the acid. k'' is calculated from the equation,

$$\ln k'' = 29.27 - 17480/RT \text{ (Fraenkel, } Z. \text{ physikal. Chem., 1907, } \mathbf{60}, 202).$$

The researches of Goldschmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **70**, 627), Bredig (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1912, **18**, 535), Sneath (ibid., p. 539) and Dawson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 2135) have indicated that the molecules

of undissociated acid as well as hydrogen ions possess definite catalytic properties. Dawson extended the hypothesis of dual catalysis by ascribing catalytic effects to all the molecular and ionic species present. The influence of acetic acid as a solvent was referred to in Part I of this series (Telang and Nadkarny, *loc. cit.*) and in view of the catalytic effects due to undissociated as well as ionised acetic acid, the influence of acetic acid on the kinetics of the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction merited further investigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The reaction was carried out at 50° for two hours in each case in the manner previously described (Telang and Nadkarny, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (alcoholic) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + 0.5 c.c. of 0.565*N*-acetic acid + x c.c. of 4*N*- KNO_3 made up to 100 c.c. with water.

x .	Electrolyte (added) concentration. [?]	Titre ($N/200\text{I}_2$).	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
0.5 c.c.	0.02 <i>N</i>	12.3 c.c.	258.9
1.0	0.04	12.1	255.2
2.5	0.1	12.0	253.2
10.0	0.4	15.0	318.4
15.0	0.6	16.6	353.0
20.0	0.8	16.8	358.7

TABLE II

(Based on Table I). $k''_{50^\circ} = 8.252$.

Total electrolyte concentration.	$k_{50^\circ} \times 10^6$.	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^5$.
0.04 <i>N</i>	92.7	1.12
0.06	84.0	1.018 ³
0.12	67.0	0.812
0.42	57.2	0.693
0.62	41.8	0.507
0.82	—	—

TABLE III.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (alcoholic) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid + x c.c. of $4N\text{-NaNO}_3$ made up to 100 c.c. with water.

x .	Electrolyte concentration.	Titre.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
Nil	Nil	8.2 c.c.	172.6
0.5 c.c.	0.02 N	9.1	184.2
1.0	0.04	8.5	178.4
2.5	0.1	9.6	203.3
5.0	0.2	9.5	201.4
7.5	0.3	11.6	245.6
10.0	0.4	11.6	245.6
20.0	0.8	12.4	260.8
40.0	1.6	13.8	291.6

TABLE IV.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (in acetic acid) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + x c.c. of $4N\text{-NaNO}_3$ made up to 100 c.c. with water.

x .	Electrolyte concentration.	Titre.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
Nil	Nil	9.3 c.c.	195.6
0.5 c.c.	0.02 N	8.1	170.7
1.0	0.04	7.8	163.0
2.5	0.1	7.9	165.0
5.0	0.2	9.3	195.6
10.0	0.4	9.5	201.4
20.0	0.8	10.3	216.8

TABLE V.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (alcoholic) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + x c.c. of buffer made up to 100 c.c. with water. The buffer consisted of 25 c.c. of 0.565 N -acetic acid + 75 c.c. of 1 N -Na-acetate in a total volume of 100 c.c. of buffer.

x .	Titre.	Acetate ion concentration.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
0.5 c.c.	10.6 c.c.	0.0038 N	222.5
1.0	9.7	0.0075	205.2
2.5	8.4	0.0188	176.5
5.0	10.0	0.0375	211.0
10.0	10.4	0.075	218.7
15.0	12.7	0.1125	268.5
20.0	14.2	0.150	301.1
40.0	18.8	0.30	400.2

TABLE VI.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (alcoholic) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + x c.c. of buffer made up to 100 c.c. with water. The buffer consisted of 50 c.c. of 0.565*N*-acetic acid + 50 c.c. of 1*N*-Na-acetate in a total volume of 100 c.c. of buffer.

x .	Titre.	Acetate ion concentration.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
0.5 c.c.	11.0 c.c.	0.0025 <i>N</i>	232.1
1.0	9.1	0.005	184.2
2.5	9.2	0.0125	193.7
5.0	8.6	0.025	180.3
10.0	9.7	0.05	205.2
15.0	10.3	0.075	216.8
20.0	10.8	0.10	228.2
40.0	14.4	0.20	305.0

TABLE VII.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + 5 c.c. of 0.565*N*-acetic acid + x c.c. of 1*N*-Na-acetate made up to 100 c.c. with water.

x .	Titre.	Acetate ion concentration.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
0.5 c.c.	10.4 c.c.	0.005 <i>N</i>	218.7
1.0	9.5	0.01	201.4
2.5	8.8	0.025	186.1
5.0	10.1	0.05	193.7
10.0	11.6	0.10	245.6
15.0	13.5	0.15	285.9
20.0	14.5	0.20	306.9
40.0	23.95	0.40	514.0

TABLE VIII.

10 C.c. of $N/5\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ (alcoholic) + 10 c.c. of $N/5\text{-K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ + x c.c. of 0.565*N*-acetic acid made up to 100 c.c. with water.

x .	Titre.	Velocity constant ($k \times 10^6$).	Concentration of the acid (c).	\sqrt{c} .	$(k/\sqrt{c}) \times 10^6$.
0.5 c.c.	11.2 c.c.	236.0	0.00284 <i>N</i>	0.0533	4432
1.0	7.8	163.0	0.00567	0.0753	2165
2.5	8.7	184.2	0.01418	0.1191	1547
5.0	8.6	180.3	0.02835	0.1684	1071
7.5	10.3	216.8	0.04253	0.2062	1052
10.0	10.7	226.3	0.0567	0.2381	950.4
15.0	10.4	218.7	0.08505	0.2917	749.9

DISCUSSION.

Secondary Electrolyte Effect.

In Table II, it is observed that the hydrogen ion-concentration decreases steadily till it reaches the minimum value at a concentration of 0.82 *N* of the electrolyte. The values of k_{50}° given are corrected for the catalytic effect of added KNO_3 , and also for the initial reaction velocity in the absence of acetic acid catalyst. Hence neglecting the small catalytic effects of acetate ions and undissociated acetic acid molecules, the k_{50}° values given represent the velocity due to hydrogen ions only. The total electrolyte concentration also includes the potassium persulphate concentration. The k values evaluated from the equation

$$k = \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{c - [\text{H}^+]}$$

where c is the acid concentration, also run in a similar way as the hydrogen-ion concentration. Apparently this is rather unusual in the sense that according to theory, the "secondary electrolyte effect" for acetic acid catalysis should be positive. In order to confirm the results, two more experiments were performed with higher concentrations of acetic acid and the results are given in Tables III and IV. It is seen from these tables, that the velocity increases at the first addition of salt and then begins to decrease. These observations are unlike Dawson's results where this change was observed at comparatively high salt concentrations. It may be of interest to note that the resultant velocities in this reaction tend to decrease, at first pass through a minimum and then again increase. This is probably due to the primary catalytic effect of the added electrolyte.

Catalytic Coefficients of Acetate Ions and of Molecules of Acetic Acid.

k_a , the catalytic coefficient of the acetate ion and k_m , that of the undissociated molecule of acetic acid have been calculated by employing three different methods (*vide* Glasstone, "Recent Advances in General Chemistry", 1936), Chapter VIII. These terms are evaluated graphically. Experiment shows that the molecules of undissociated acid have a negative catalytic coefficient. The results obtained by all the three methods are of the same order of magnitude although the actual figures may show slight differences.

In accordance with the equation, $V = k_a x + k_m c$, if x is plotted against V , the reaction velocity passes through a fairly sharp minimum and then

begins to increase in a linear manner as the salt concentration is increased (*vide* Table VII). The slope of this line $k_A = 0.9 \times 10^{-3}$, and its intercept when extrapolated to cut the V -axis ($x=0$), $k_{Mc} = -2.5 \times 10^{-6}$, hence $k_M = -0.9 \times 10^{-3}$. (While calculating k_{Mc} , the initial reaction velocity in the absence of the catalyst was taken into consideration).

According to the equation

$$V/\sqrt{c} = (k_M + k_A - k_M)\sqrt{k} + k_M\sqrt{c},$$

if V/\sqrt{c} is plotted (Table VIII) against \sqrt{c} , a straight line representing the variation of the reaction velocity with the concentration of the acid is anticipated. But in this experiment it is not so. The values of V/\sqrt{c} decrease rapidly at first and then gradually decrease in a linear manner with increasing \sqrt{c} . From this behaviour, it is clear that the hydrogen-ion concentration cannot be neglected in very dilute solutions. For purposes of evaluating the required constant, the slope of the line at higher concentrations, where the representation is a linear function, is considered. Hence the slope $k_M = -2.0 \times 10^{-3}$.

By employing equations,

$$k_A = \frac{l'q - lq'}{q - q'} \text{ and } k_M = \frac{l - l'}{q - q'},$$

$k_A = 1.35 \times 10^{-3}$, and $k_M = -1.06 \times 10^{-3}$ (Tables V and VI).

Attention may be drawn to the solvent effect of acetic acid as given in Part I (Telang and Nadkarny, *loc. cit.*). It was observed that the velocity in presence of acetic acid remained practically unaltered. The reaction is highly catalysed by hydrogen ions and the velocity in acetic acid should have increased correspondingly. Whatever acceleration may be produced by hydrogen and acetate ions may be counterbalanced by the retardation due to molecules of undissociated acetic acid. Hence, probably, no change in the reaction velocity with acetic acid as the solvent is observed.